

Studies on the Peptide and Amino Acids of *Pueraria tuberosa*

MOHD. ALI* and JAMAL S. QADRY**

Hamdard College of Pharmacy (University of Delhi), Hamdard Nagar, New Delhi-110 062

Manuscript received 8 October 1985, revised 5 May 1986, accepted 2 August 1986

Free amino acids and proteinic material are detected in the water extract of *Pueraria tuberosa*. By using chromatographic techniques fourteen unbound amino acids are identified. The nature of the protein is found to be oligopeptide which on acid hydrolysis gives eight amino acids.

THE tuberous roots of *Pueraria tuberosa* DC (Leguminosae) are used in medicine¹⁻³ as aphrodisiac, tonic, galactagogue, diuretic, emetic, and alterative. They are consumed as supplementary food and for birth control by certain Indian tribes. The tubers have been reported to contain sterols⁴, isoflavones⁴, and pterocarponoids⁵⁻⁷. Atal and Qadry⁸ have examined different samples of tubers and reported the presence of large quantities of proteins and amino acids. The present work is undertaken to find out the nature of free and bound amino acids and to analyse the composition of the peptide.

Experimental

Separation of free amino acids: The powdered drug was extracted with aqueous alcohol. The extract was filtered, concentrated under vacuum, and made free from peptide by adding absolute ethanol. The supernatant liquid containing free amino acids was treated with chloroform to remove lipids. It was then filtered, concentrated, and used as such for chromatographic separation.

Hydrolysis of peptide: The precipitated proteinic material was purified with absolute alcohol to remove any free amino acid. It was hydrolysed with mixture of concentrated hydrochloric acid and formic acid (4 : 1) for 2 h. The acid mixture was removed under reduced pressure and the residue dissolved in a small amount of water. The solution was re-evaporated and the residue again dissolved in water. It was neutralised by adding dilute solution of ammonia and then dried. The amino acid mixture so obtained was dissolved in a small amount of water and extracted with water saturated n-butanol to remove the neutral amino acids from the hydrolysate. The extract and the remaining solution containing acidic and basic amino acids after filtration and concentration was subjected to paper chromatography and tlc. The amino acids

were visualised with ninhydrin reagent on drying at 100° for 10 min.

Results and Discussion

The water extract of the powdered tuber gives positive ninhydrin test indicating the presence of free amino acids in the root. After the removal of protein and lipids, chromatographic studies were carried out to analyse and identify the amino acids present. The n-butanol-glacial acetic acid-water (4 : 1 : 1) and phenol-water (3 : 1) systems were found to be most satisfactory for separation. In these systems, fourteen coloured spots on chromatographic paper strips in descending manner and twelve spots on chromatoplates using silica gel G were detected when the mixture was run for 18 and 5 h, respectively. The spots were identified by comparing their R_f values with the reference samples and fluorescence before as well as after spraying ninhydrin reagent. We also employed Brenner and Niederwieser's⁹ two-dimensional technique for the separation of amino acids mixture using n-butanol-glacial acetic acid-water (4 : 1 : 1) in one direction and phenol-water (3 : 1) in the other on a paper chromatogram and all the fourteen spots were visualised. The attempts to analyse the mixture on tlc in such pattern were not successful.

The extract after removal of protein gave negative tests for tannins and polysaccharides but positive test of saponins. The precipitate was found to be peptidic in nature since it underwent autolysis when kept in water for about one week and gave all tests of proteins¹⁰. The precipitate was protamine in nature since it was readily soluble in distilled water, 60% alcohol, and in acids and alkalis as mentioned by Karlson¹¹. Albumin and globulins were absent in the protein. It was of lower molecular weight since no interface film was formed on addition of chloroform to the aqueous solution of the precipitate as indicated by Trease¹².

Present address : * Regional Research Laboratory (C.S.I.R.), Ministry of Public Health, P.O. Box 5, Saffat, Kuwait.

Canal Road, Jammu; Tawi-180-001. **Islamic Medicine Centre,

TABLE I—FREE AND PROTEIN BOUND AMINO ACIDS OF *Pueraria tuberosa* ROOT

Sl. no.	Amino acids*	<i>R_f</i> values**				Spot colour
		<i>P_c</i>		<i>T_{lc}</i>		
		System C Time E	System D Time F	System C Time G	System D Time H	
1.	Alanine ^a	0.369	0.442	0.073	0.365	Violet
2.	Arginine ^a	0.141	0.576	0.273	0.287	Violet
3.	Asparagine ^b	0.745	0.262	0.214	0.256	Pink
4.	Citrulline ^b	0.172	0.490	0.239	0.439	Violet
5.	Glutamic acid ^{a,b}	0.290	0.200	0.301	0.146	Yellow
6.	Glycine ^b	0.218	0.317	0.200	0.268	Violet
7.	Histidine ^b	0.232	0.615	0.121	0.380	Greenish
8.	Hydroxyproline ^b	0.200	0.605	0.110	0.507	Yellow
9.	Isoleucine ^{a,b}	0.469	0.746	0.492	0.673	Pink
10.	Leucine ^{a,b}	0.536	0.742	0.546	0.583	Violet
11.	Lysine ^b	0.112	0.330	0.390	0.111	Yellow
12.	Methionine ^b	0.456	0.628	0.400	0.546	Violet
13.	Phenylalanine ^a	0.501	0.686	0.390	0.682	Violet
14.	Proline ^{a,b}	0.445	0.659	0.117	0.585	Green
15.	Serine ^{a,b}	0.116	0.163	0.227	0.146	Pink
16.	Threonine ^b	0.245	0.432	0.190	0.268	Red
17.	Valine ^b	0.520	0.538	0.487	0.507	Pink

* Nature of amino acids : ^a Protein bound ; ^b Free. ** Solvent system : C=n-butanol-glacial acetic acid-water (4 : 1 : 1), D=phenol-water (3 : 1, w/v) ; Time (h) : E=18 (distance travelled by solvent front=55 cm), F=17 (52 cm), G=5 (20.5 cm), H=4.5 (20.5 cm).

The higher glycine derivative might be absent because the 60% ethanolic solution of the precipitate when chromatographed using water saturated phenol and in cresol saturated with water did not show separation at all. Such derivatives do not give colour reaction with ninhydrin¹⁰. Besides, a tailing was observed only after heating the unsprayed chromatogram and viewing under uv light. All these tests indicate that the precipitate consists only of oligopeptide having six to ten amino acids.

The protein on subjection to acid hydrolysis gave a mixture of amino acids. The results of resolution of free and bound amino acids are summarised in Table I.

References

1. K. R. KIRTIKAR and B. D. BASU, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Lahit Mohan Basu, Allahabad, 1933, Vol. I, p. 792.
2. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 207.
3. G. WATT, "Dictionary of the Economic Products of India", Periodical Experts, Delhi, 1972, Vol. VI, p. 363.
4. S. P. BHUTANI, S. S. CHIBBER and T. R. SESHADRI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 210.
5. B. S. JOSHI, V. N. KAMAT and T. R. GOVINDACHARI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 1112.
6. B. S. JOSHI and V. N. KAMAT, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. I*, 1973, 907.
7. A. V. K. PRASHAD, R. S. KAPIL and S. P. POPII, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1985, 24, 236.
8. C. K. ATAL and S. M. J. S. QADRY, *J. Sci. Ind. Res., Sect. C*, 1962, 21, 184.
9. M. BRENNER and A. NIEDERWISER, *Experientia*, 1960, 16, 378.
10. E. LEDERER and M. LEDERER, "Chromatography", 2nd ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1957, pp. 306, 333.
11. P. KARLSON, "Introduction to Modern Biochemistry", 3rd ed., Academic, New York, 1968, pp. 21, 35, 43.
12. G. E. TREASE, "A Textbook of Pharmacognosy", 8th ed., Bailliere Tindall Cassel, London, 1961, p. 588.